

**SYNTHESIS IN THE ALLOXAZINE, ISOALLOXAZINE
(FLAVIN) AND LUMAZINE GROUPS. PART II.
SYNTHESIS OF SOME AMINO DERI-
VATIVES OF ALLOXAZINE
AND THIOALLOXAZINE.**

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In attempting to explore new methods of synthesis of compounds of the alloxazine group with substituents in benzene ring, it has been found that 1:2:4-triaminobenzene condenses with violuric acid yielding an amino-alloxazine, similar to the condensation product of violuric acid with *m*-phenylenediamine. Thiovioluric acid, like violuric acid, condenses with *m*-phenylenediamine to yield an amino-2-thioalloxazine. These compounds are expected to be of use in some chemotherapeutic investigations.

Since the synthesis of alloxazines with various substituents in the benzene ring by the method of Kuhn requires the corresponding substituted *ortho*-diamines, which are not easily accessible, it has now been tried to explore other possible methods for their synthesis. It has been reported by Kuhn and Cook (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 763) that the synthesis of alloxazine by the condensations of (a) *o*-aminophenol with uramil, (b) bromobarbituric acid with *o*-phenylenediamine, and (c) aniline with violuric acid was not successful. Piloty (*Annalen*, 1904, 333, 44), however, condensed *m*-phenylenediamine with violuric acid and obtained a dyestuff which he called "ureidamidoazine." From its physical properties he regarded it to be an azine of the quinoxaline group but has refrained from suggesting a definite formula though he appears to favour its formulation as 7-aminoalloxazine (I, R = NH₂; R₁ = R₂ = H) also adopted in Beilstein's Handbook (Bd. XXIV, p. 507; Bd. XXVI, p. 591). The British Chemical Abstracts (1904, i, 821) have, however, recorded the formula (II). In justification of the assignment of the alloxazine structure to this compound, it has now been found, besides other properties (*vide* experimental), that it yields with excess of diazomethane only a *trimethyl* derivative which can be represented by (III) on the basis of the formula (I) for the original compound.

(I)

(II)

(III)

The condensation of violuric acid with *m*-phenylenediamine to yield an alloxazine can theoretically proceed in two directions to furnish either 7-aminoalloxazine or 5-aminoalloxazine (I. $R = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = NH_2$) according as the oximino group of violuric acid condenses in the *ortho*- or the *para*-position to the unattacked amino group in *m*-phenylenediamine. It is generally known that a substituent in the benzene ring (in the *meta* position to the group participating in the cyclisation) always activates the *para*-position in preference to the *ortho*; but in some particular cases the cyclisation has actually been shown to take place in the *ortho*-position (Späth and Kruta, *Monatsh.*, 1928, 50, 341; *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1024; *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 26, 177): It appeared, therefore, to be of interest to condense 1:2:4-triaminebenzene hydrochloride with alloxan which can yield either 7-aminoalloxazine or 6-aminoalloxazine (I, $R_1 = NH_2$; $R = R_2 = H$) or both. This condensation proceeded very readily to yield an aminoalloxazine derivative, which apparently resembles the compound obtained from *m*-phenylenediamine and violuric acid, but the identity could not be proved by mixed melting point since neither of them melt below 350°. However, the compound obtained by Piloty is provisionally considered to be 7-aminoalloxazine.

From the fact that *m*-phenylenediamine very readily undergoes condensation with violuric acid to yield an alloxazine, whereas aniline does not, it was surmised that the activation of the *o*-position to the amino group by a substituent in the *m*-position is essential and it was hoped that the *m*-substituted anilines might condense with violuric acid to yield the corresponding alloxazines. But with *m*-toluidine (also *p*-), *m*-aminophenol, *m*-nitroaniline, *m*-aminophenylurea and *m*-aminoacetanilide no condensation product could be isolated, all this yielding blue unstable compounds which are probably the salts of violuric acid with the amines (Zerewitinoff, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4804). *o*- and *p*-phenylenediamines yielded some products which are not alloxazines; β -naphthylamine, wherein the *o*-position is known to

be very reactive, also did not condense. From these results it appears that the *m*-amino group is absolutely specific for this type of condensation.

Since the sulphur atom present in an organic molecule is known to impart to it specific bactericidal properties and plays a prominent part in the chemotherapy of tuberculosis (it being present in all the gold preparations now current), an attempt was made to introduce the thiol group in the benzene ring of alloxazine. Since this offered some difficulties in the actual working, attention was next directed to the synthesis of compounds of 2-thioalloxazine group (IV, R=H) which can exist in the tautomeric form (V, R=H) so as to form the aurothio (-S. Au) compound with gold salts. 2-Thioalloxazine could not be prepared by condensing *o*-phenylenediamine with 2-thioalloxan, since the latter itself is not yet known (*cf.* Robinson and Tomlison, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 467). So opportunity was now taken to synthesise a derivative of thioalloxazine by using thiovioluric acid. Thiovioluric acid, similarly as violuric acid, did not condense with aniline, but with *m*-phenylenediamine it furnished an amino-2-thioalloxazine which can be represented as (IV, R=NH₂) or its tautomeric form. This compound exhibits properties characteristic of the alloxazines.

(IV)

(V)

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of m-Phenylenediamine with Violuric Acid.—The 7-aminoalloxazine was prepared essentially according to the conditions of Piloty (*loc. cit.*). To a boiling solution of *m*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and violuric acid (0.5 g.) in water (15 c.c.) a solution of caustic soda (10%, 2 c.c.) was added whereby the condensation product began to separate as a brick red powder. After boiling for a few minutes, the reaction mixture was cooled, allowed to stand for a few hours, filtered, and the solid washed with a little boiling water, yield 0.8 g. It was obtained from a large volume of water as

a red powder which appears to be crystalline under a high power microscope; not melting at 350° . [Found: N, 30.22; Formula I ($R = NH_2$, $R_1 = R_2 = H$) $C_{10}H_7O_2N_3$ requires N, 30.57 per cent. Formula (II) $C_{10}H_5O_3N_3$ requires N, 28.34 per cent]. It is fairly soluble in pyridine forming a red solution with a pronounced green fluorescence indicating an alloxazine structure. It is very stable to alkali; after boiling with 15 parts of caustic soda (10%) for 3 hours, a yellow compound crystallising from water in slender yellow needles was obtained which appears to be the sodium salt since on acidifying its aqueous solution the original dyestuff is obtained. Due to the very sparing solubility of the dyestuff, it was difficult to react the compound with benzaldehyde, isocyanates, etc. and isolate the pure reaction products in good yields.

Trimethyl Derivative (III).—Finely powdered aminoalloxazine (1 g.) was allowed to stand with occasional shaking for a day with an ethereal solution (100 c. c.) of diazomethane obtained from nitrosomethylurea (5 g.), the first few hours being in ice and then at the room temperature. The ether was distilled off and the residue so obtained was crystallised from formic acid as microcrystalline red powder not melting at 345° . (Found: N, 25.66. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N_5$ requires N, 25.82 per cent).

1:2:4-Triaminobenzene can very conveniently be prepared as the hydrochloride by the reduction of Bismark brown with tin foil and hydrochloric acid according to the method of Berthel (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2276) or by the reduction of 2:4-dinitroaniline (which in its turn was obtained from 2:5-dinitroacetanilide) with tin and hydrochloric acid (Hinsberg, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1253).

For the preparation of the required 2:4-dinitroacetanilide, the method of Rudnew (*Z. Chem.*, 1871, 7, 202) yields only 25 g. of the nitrated product from 40 g. of acetanilide. On carrying the nitration at about $30-35^{\circ}$, the nitrated product was obtained only as a gum. After many trials the method described below was found to give the dinitro product as the sole product in very good yield.

Finely powdered acetanilide (20 g.) was gradually added with good stirring to a mixture of fuming nitric acid ($d 1.51$, 500 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid ($d 1.84$, 200 c.c.) during 45 minutes. By adjusting the rate of addition and cooling the acid mixture with water, the temperature was kept between $30-35^{\circ}$. After the addition of acetanilide was over, the solution was kept stirring for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then slowly poured into ice (about 5 lbs.) when the dinitro compound separated gradually in a yellow crystalline form and collected as a foam. After $\frac{1}{2}$ hour it was filtered,

washed thoroughly with water and dried, yield 27-28 g. It was dissolved in boiling benzene (150 c.c.), rapidly filtered and on allowing the clear green solution to cool, the dinitro compound separated in long needles (24.5 g.). From the mother liquors some more of the product (2 g.) was obtained.

2 : 4-Dinitroacetanilide crystallises from benzene in beautiful yellow needles with a green tinge which becomes very light yellow on drying. It melts at 125-26° (decomp.) (lit. m.p. 120°).

In the course of the hydrolysis to 2 : 4-dinitroaniline it was found that when potassium hydroxide was first added to the acetyl compound and then alcohol, a vigorous reaction took place and after refluxing for about 15 minutes, a product separated which crystallised from water in beautiful golden yellow needles, m.p. about 325° (decomp.). This detonates very violently on heating in a capillary tube in a free flame so that the combustion of this compound was not attempted. It is neither 2 : 4-dinitrophenol nor the quinonoid salt of nitronic acid corresponding to 2 : 4-dinitroaniline described by Green and Rowe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 508). This is being further investigated (*cf.* Cohn and Springer, *Monatsh.*, 1903, 24, 90).

Condensation of 1 : 2 : 4-Triaminobenzene and Alloxan.—On mixing a clear solution of 1 : 2 : 4-triaminobenzene hydrochloride (2 g. in 20 c.c.) containing a little boric acid with a hot solution of alloxan (1.2 g. in 25 c.c.) a turbidity appeared and the condensation product began to separate as a brick-red powder. The whole was warmed on the steam-bath for 5 minutes, cooled, filtered and washed with water, yield 0.9 g. It separated from a large volume of water as a red crystalline powder, not melting at 350°. (Found : N, 30.21. $C_{10}H_7O_2N_5$ requires N, 30.57 per cent). In appearance it resembles the product from *m*-phenylenediamine and violuric acid. Its aqueous solution shows a green fluorescence. It dissolves in alkali to an orange-red solution showing a green fluorescence.

7-Amino-2-thioalloxazine.—*m*-Phenylenediamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and thiovioluric acid (1 g.) were dissolved in boiling water (30 c.c.) and to the clear filtered solution aqueous sodium hydroxide (10 %, 4 c.c.) was added and boiled for a few minutes. The well cooled solution was filtered and the brown product obtained was thoroughly washed with hot water, alcohol, ether and dried (0.8 g.). It is a brown crystalline powder not melting up to 340°. (Found : N, 28.22 ; S, 12.76. $C_{10}H_7ON_5S$ requires N, 28.57 ; S, 13.06 per cent). It is very sparingly soluble in all solvents

excepting pyridine in which it shows an intense green fluorescence. It dissolves in alkali (more readily on warming) to an orange solution with a green fluorescence. With concentrated hydrochloric and sulphuric acids, it shows the characteristic red colourations. It is easily desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury.

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